

PSYCHOLINGUISTIC ASPECTS OF THE TRANSLATION IN THE WORK OF GUIDE-INTERPRETER (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE UNITED STATES).

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Annotation: The work of a guide-interpreter is inextricably linked to psycholinguistic aspects that play an important role in effective interaction and communication with tourists. In general, psycholinguistic aspects play an important role in the work of a tour guide, helping to establish effective communication, maintain tourists' attention and understanding, and create a comfortable and trusting atmosphere during the tour. In this article we will discuss the work of a tour guide and what psycholinguistic aspects are important for effective work.

Keywords: Guide-interpreter, psycholinguistic aspects, importance of the work, communication and interaction.

The work of a guide-interpreter is multifaceted and involves several important aspects. Here is a detailed explanation of the work of a guide-interpreter:

- **Preparation and research:** A guide-interpreter starts his work by thoroughly preparing and researching the place he will be showing tourists. He studies the history, culture, traditions, geography and other aspects related to the place in order to be armed with the necessary information to convey to the tourists. This includes reading books, studying sources, visiting museums and historical sites, and interacting with locals.

- **Development of itineraries and programmes:** The tour guide develops itineraries and tour programmes based on the interests and needs of the group of tourists. He chooses the sights, museums, monuments, parks, and other places that are most relevant to the theme of the tour. The guide-translator takes into account logistical aspects such as time, accessibility and other factors to ensure that the tour goes smoothly.
- **Translation and Interpretation:** One of the main aspects of the interpreter guide's job is translation and interpretation. During the tour, the guide-interpreter translates and explains information about a place, its history, culture, architecture and other aspects into the tourists' native language. He or she knows how to convey information in an easy to understand and interesting way, using appropriate language tools and examples. The guide-interpreter can also answer questions and clarify information to ensure tourists' full understanding.
- **Communication and interaction:** The guide has excellent communication skills and is able to interact effectively with the group of tourists. He/she creates a welcoming atmosphere, establishes rapport with each member of the group and strives to meet their needs. The guide uses sign language, facial expressions, non-verbal communication and other techniques to enhance the understanding and engagement of the tourists.
- **Cultural competence:** The guide has a deep understanding of the culture and traditions of the place he/she is showing and can convey this information to tourists. He explains the nuances and peculiarities of the culture and helps to understand local customs, traditions, etiquette and social norms. The interpreter guide can also help group members to avoid cultural blunders and inappropriate actions, which promotes mutual understanding and respect between different cultures.

- **Group safety and management:** The interpreter is responsible for the safety and management of the group of tourists during the tour. He/she informs the tourists about safety rules, dangerous places or situations, and ensures their well-being. The interpreter is also able to manage group dynamics, resolve conflicts, ensure equal distribution of time and attention among group members.
- **Personalisation and flexibility:** The tour guide is ready to adapt to the needs and preferences of each group of tourists. He/she can modify the itinerary, add or remove stops, suggest additional activities or make recommendations depending on the interests and capabilities of the group. The interpreter guide reacts flexibly to changes in plans and strives to create the most satisfactory experience for the tourists.

The job of an interpreter guide requires a wide range of skills, including knowledge of the area being explored, language competence, communication skills, cultural sensitivity, group management and organisational abilities. This profession plays an important role in creating positive tourist experiences, exchanging cultures and mutual understanding between people of different countries and nationalities.

There are several key factors that distinguish an interpreter guide from a simple guide:

- **Language skills:** One of the main differences is language skills. A guide-interpreter knows not only the mother tongue but also the language of the tourists he/she is working with. He is able to translate and interpret information in different languages to ensure understanding and communication between a group of tourists and the local context. At the same time, a simple guide only works in one language and does not perform the function of translation.

- **Education and training:** Guide interpreters usually have special education or have completed specialised courses in the field of translation and tourism. This allows them to acquire skills in interpreting, adapting and interacting with international tourist groups. Ordinary guides may have education or experience in the tourism industry, but are not necessarily specialized in translation and languages.
- **Functions and tasks:** The guide-interpreter has a dual role - he or she not only gives tours and provides information about places, but also translates into the tourists' native language. He or she translates speech and explanations, answers questions and ensures that tourists understand the local context. A simple guide, on the other hand, focuses on giving tours, providing information and answering tourists' questions in the same language.
- **Need for language services:** The work of a guide-interpreter is most needed when a group of tourists speaks a language other than the language of the place they are visiting. A guide-interpreter provides interpretation and helps tourists understand and enjoy the tour. A simple guide may be preferable when tourists speak the same language as the locals and do not require interpretation.

In general, the job of an interpreter guide is more specialised and requires additional interpretation skills and language knowledge. It provides tourists with the opportunity to understand and interact with the local context in their own language, making the tourist experience more comfortable and informative.

The work of a guide-interpreter plays an important role in the field of tourism and intercultural communication. Here are some aspects that highlight the importance of this profession:

- **Information transfer:** A guide-interpreter serves as a link between tourists and the place they are visiting. He or she provides a variety of information about the attractions, history, culture, traditions and other aspects of the place. The guide interpreter translates and explains the content in the tourists' native language, making the visit more interesting and understandable.
- **Interpretation of cultural differences:** The guide-interpreter has a good understanding of the culture of the country or place he is showing and can help tourists understand the local customs, traditions and nuances. He or she can help to overcome language and cultural barriers, which contributes to a better understanding of local culture and creates a positive experience for tourists.
- **Safety and comfort:** The interpreter guide is responsible for the safety and comfort of the tourists during the tour. He/she can provide information on safety, rules of conduct and help in case of problems. This is especially important for foreign tourists who may feel insecure in an unfamiliar environment.
- **Personalization and flexibility:** The tour guide can adapt the tour to the individual needs and interests of the group of tourists. He can take into account tourists' preferences, modify the itinerary or add additional stops to make the experience more unique and meet the needs of each group member.
- **Creating memorable experiences:** The interpreter guide's job is to create an unforgettable experience for the tourists. He or she can offer interesting stories, anecdotes, legends that will bring places to life and make the visit memorable. An interpreter guide is able to create an atmosphere in which tourists feel involved and inspired.

The work of a guide-interpreter is important for a successful and quality

tourist experience. It helps to make the visit more informative, comprehensible, safe and interesting and promotes cultural exchange and understanding between different cultures and peoples.

The role of a guide-interpreter in the USA has several psycholinguistic aspects that help ensure effective communication between the guide and tourists from different countries. Here are some of them:

- **Language adaptation:** A guide-interpreter must have good translation and interpretation skills to convey information fluently in the tourists' native language. He must be familiar with the cultural nuances and be able to adapt his speech to the level of understanding of the tourist group.
- **Communication skills:** The guide-interpreter should be able to communicate effectively with tourists and make contact with different people. This includes the use of sign language, facial expressions and other non-verbal means of communication to enhance understanding and convey information.
- **Cultural competence:** The guide-interpreter should have a good understanding of the tourists' culture and adapt his/her explanations and comments to cultural differences. This helps to provide an in-depth understanding of U.S. attractions and history, and improves the overall travel experience for tourists.
- **Psychological empathy:** A tour guide must be sensitive to the emotional needs of tourists and able to manage group dynamics. He/she may encounter different types of personalities and must be able to create a trusting relationship with the tourists to meet their needs during the tour.
- **Intercultural communication:** The guide-interpreter should be able to take into account language and cultural barriers and overcome them when communicating with tourists from different countries. This

includes the ability to recognise unspoken cues and use cultural codes to make communication more effective.

- Flexibility and adaptability: The guide-interpreter should be flexible and able to adapt quickly to changing conditions and the needs of tourists. This may include changing the itinerary, modifying the schedule or additional comments and explanations depending on the interests and requirements of the group.

These psycholinguistic aspects play an important role in the success of a guide-interpreter in the USA and help create an enjoyable and informative experience for tourists.

References:

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Fillmore Ch., D.T. Langendoen (eds.) (1971) Studies in Linguistic Semantics.

New York, Holt, Rinehard and Winston, Inc.

Gentzier E. (1993) Contemporary Translation Theories. London-New York, Routledge.

Gernsbacher M. A. (ed.) (1994) Handbook of Psycholinguistics. New York, Academic Press.

Gutknecht Ch., L. J. Rolle (1996) Translating by Factors. New York, State University of New York Press.

House J., S. Blum-Kulka (eds.) (1986) Interlingual and Intercultural Communication. Discourse and Cognition in Translation and Second Language Acquisition Studies. Tübingen, Günter Narr Verlag.

Jackendoff R. (1993) Language of the Mind. Cambridge, Mass., M. I. T. Press.

Jakobson R. (1992) On Linguistic Aspects of Translation. In: Schulte R., J. Biguenet (eds.): 144-151.

Johnson-Laird P. N., P. C. Wason (eds.) (1980) Thinking in Cognitive Science.

Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.